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REYNES L. SUMAYLO

Instructor III

West Visayas State University-Calinog Campus

sumaylo.reynes@wvsu.edu.ph

“PROMISES LEFT IN THE DARK”

You said you would not make me cry,
but tears still fall and questions fly;
you promised love would never end,
yet left my heart too hard to mend.

You said I was your only one,
but there she stood beneath your sun;
you called me angel, soft and bright,
yet made my days feel dark as night.

You asked for trust, my whole, my all,
then watched that faithful promise fall;
I gave my heart without defense,
and found your doubts were more intense.

I saw her arms around you tight,
and both of you looked warm with light;
now tell me, should I take the blame
for hearing whispers speak your name?

You threw harsh words that cut too deep,
they stayed with me and stole my sleep;
you filled the night with reasons why,
while I was left to break and cry.

Why do you hurt the heart you knew?
What kind of joy is this for you?
Is pain the prize you want to keep,
or just a game you play too deep?

You said you loved me, yet you fled,
you never fought for what you said;
were all your vows at last untrue,

or was I a fool to trust in you?

